

DKRZ Data Pool Content		http://bit.ly/IPCC_DKRZ_Data							
Date:	2019-08-16		Tape/CERA:	http://cera-www.dkrz.de					
Author:	M. Stockhause (stockhause@dkrz.de)		Disk (Mistral):	/pool/data (partly under construction)					
*Data Reference: see section 'How to find data references' in:		https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HAIQyU02x5BrHz05HEu0v6lFiRBHZfPAYMsD349uiyo							
+CERA data: account required; use of jblob for script-based data access:		https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDC/ce/ceasearch/info?site=jblob							
Project	Data	Destination	Disk/Tape+	Origin/Owner	License	Data Reference*	More Information	Contact	Comment
CMIP5 / AR5	IPCC AR5 Reference Data Archive	https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDC/ce/ceasearch/q?general_key_ss=IPCC-DDC&project_acronym_ss=IPCC-AR5_CMIP5	Tape/CERA	multiple	scientific use only for MIROC/NICAM; all other data is also for commercial use	see on landing pages	http://www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/index.html	data@dkrz.de	Also accessible via ESGF - select data node: 'esgf2.dkrz.de'
CMIP5 / AR5	CMIP5 Subset	/work/kd0956/CMIP5/data	Disk	multiple	scientific use only for MIROC/NICAM; all other data is also for commercial use	see on landing pages	http://www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/index.html	data@dkrz.de	
CMIP6 / AR6	CMIP6 (AR6 Subset)	/work/ik1017/CMIP6/data	Disk	multiple	CC BY-SA 4.0	see on in ESGF or on landing pages	https://bit.ly/DKRZ_CDP	data-pool@dkrz.de	Subset according to: https://goo.gl/tVaGko
ENSEMBLES	ENSEMBLES	https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDC/ce/ceasearch/q?project_acronym_ss=ENSEMBLES	Tape/CERA	multiple	http://ensembles-eu.metoffice.com/docs/Ensembles_Data_Policy_261108.pdf	see on landing pages	-	data@dkrz.de	
ERA	ERA Interim: 2013-	/work/bm0146/k204082/ERA_INTERIM	Disk	ECMWF	Signed document required: https://www.dkrz.de/up/services/data-management/projects-and-cooperations/era/era40-1/documents	-	https://www.dkrz.de/up/services/data-management/projects-and-cooperations/era/era	data@dkrz.de	
ERA	ERA Interim: 1979-2018	https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDC/ce/ceasearch/q?project_acronym_ss=ERA_INTERIM	Tape/CERA	ECMWF	Signed document required: https://www.dkrz.de/up/services/data-management/projects-and-cooperations/era/era40-1/documents	-	https://www.dkrz.de/up/services/data-management/projects-and-cooperations/era/era	data@dkrz.de	CERA: other ERA projects also available: ERA15, ERA40; ERA20C
ERA	ERA5 (in work)	/work/bk1099/data	Disk	ECMWF	http://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/licences/copernicus/	Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) (2017): ERA5: Fifth generation of ECMWF atmospheric reanalyses of the global climate . Copernicus Climate Change Service Climate Data Store (CDS), date of access. https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/home	https://www.dkrz.de/up/services/data-management/projects-and-cooperations/era/era	data@dkrz.de	status of available data at: https://modvis.dkrz.de/bm0146/ERA5/statusE5.html
Euro-CORDEX	CORDEX (Domains EUR, AFR): native grid	https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDC/ce/ceasearch/q?project_acronym_ss=CORDEX_DDS-CMIP5_native-grid	Tape/CERA	multiple	scientific use	-	-	data@dkrz.de	
Euro-CORDEX	CORDEX (Domains EUR, AFR): regular grid	https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDC/ce/ceasearch/q?project_acronym_ss=CORDEX_DDS-CMIP5_lat-lon-grid	Tape/CERA	multiple	scientific use	-	-	data@dkrz.de	
Euro-CORDEX	CORDEX (Domains EUR, AFR)	/work/kd0956/CORDEX/data	Disk	multiple	scientific use	-	-	data@dkrz.de	
HAPPI / SR1.5	HAPPI global (AR6 subset)	/work/ik1017/HAPPI	Disk	multiple	CC BY 4.0	see on landing pages	IPCC DDC page (in work)	data@dkrz.de	Subset according to: https://goo.gl/tVaGko

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Project	Data	Destination	Disk/Tape+	Origin/Owner	License	Data Reference*	More Information	Contact	Comment
HAPPI / SR1.5	HAPPI global	https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cerasearch/q?general_key_ss=IPCC-DDC&project_acronym_ss=HAPPI	Tape/CERA	multiple	CC BY 4.0	see on landing pages	IPCC DDC page (in work)	data@dkrz.de	http://www.ipcc-data.org
ICDC:Atmosphere	Atmospheric data for model evaluation	/pool/data/ICDC/atmosphere	Disk	multiple	see on data pages	see on data pages	http://icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de/1/daten/atmosphere.html	icdc.cen@lists.uni-hamburg.de	Data collection of ICDC (CEN): http://www.icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de
ICDC:Ice+Snow	Cryospheric data for model evaluation	/pool/data/ICDC/ice_and_snow	Disk	multiple	see on data pages	see on data pages	http://icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de/1/daten/cryosphere.html	icdc.cen@lists.uni-hamburg.de	Data collection of ICDC (CEN): http://www.icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de
ICDC:Land	Land data for model evaluation	/pool/data/ICDC/land	Disk	multiple	see on data pages	see on data pages	http://icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de/1/daten/land.html	icdc.cen@lists.uni-hamburg.de	Data collection of ICDC (CEN): http://www.icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de
ICDC:Ocean	Ocean data for model evaluation	/pool/data/ICDC/ocean	Disk	multiple	see on data pages	see on data pages	http://icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de/1/daten/ocean.html	icdc.cen@lists.uni-hamburg.de	Data collection of ICDC (CEN): http://www.icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de
ICDC:Reanalyse	Reanalysis data for model evaluation	/pool/data/ICDC/reanalyses/	Disk	multiple	see on data pages	see on data pages	http://icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de/1/daten/reanalysis-atmosphere.html	icdc.cen@lists.uni-hamburg.de	Data collection of ICDC (CEN): http://www.icdc.cen.uni-hamburg.de
IPCC DDC	Reference Data Archives: AR5, AR4, TAR, SAR, parts of FAR, SR1.5	https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cerasearch/q?general_key_ss=IPCC-DDC	Tape/CERA	multiple	commercial use except for AR5 MIROC/NICAM	see on landing pages		data@dkrz.de	http://www.ipcc-data.org